

Infrared Spectra of Acidic Soils

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Fifteen acidic soils collected from different parts of India from a depth of 0-20 cm. have been taken for the study of IR-absorption curves by KBr-mull technique using Perkin-Elmer Spectrophotometer. These IR-curves of the soils were studied for their different characteristic IR-absorption peaks allotted to Si-OH (structural water-peak); Si-OH (Absorbed water-peak); Si-O (Silica peak); Al-O (Alumina peak); Si-H (pH-peak) and Si-C (Carbon-peak) functional groups. The total number of peaks in different IR-absorption regions were generally found to be 10 and this is said to be indication that the soils are useful for agricultural crop production. The most characteristic peak in such acidic soils has been found to occur mainly at 10.95 μ to 11.00 μ wavelengths which has been said to be due to the functional group, Si-H. The common peaks observed in the IR-curves of all the acidic soils are found to occur at 2.95 μ , 4.30 μ , 6.15 μ , 9.10 μ , 9.70 μ , 12.50 μ and 14.45 μ wavelengths. The regression (straight line) equations showing the relation between the depth of IR-peaks and different soil properties have also been obtained.

THE technique of infrared spectrophotometry (infrared region between 2.5 μ to 25 μ) has been widely used in organic and physical chemistry^{1,2}. But generally its application to clay and soil chemistry has not been attempted. However, De³ is probably the first who (in different infrared regions of IR-curves) characterised the IR-curves of a few representative soils of India in terms of their physico-chemical properties⁴.

In the present paper the study has been made to observe the relative characteristics of IR-curves of fifteen acidic soils collected from different parts of India. Their corresponding regression (straight line) equations representing relations between depths of IR-peaks and soil properties which are found to be significant at 5% level of significance have been reported and discussed.

Experimental

Fifteen acidic soil samples viz., soils of Mirzapur, Almorah (U.P.); Ranchi, Dhanbad (Bihar); Lakhimpur (Assam); Koraput (Orissa); Burdwan, Darjeeling (West Bengal); Godavari (Andhra Pradesh); Bangalore, Mandeya (Karnatak); Nilgiris (Tamil Nadu); Poona, Ratnagiri (Maharashtra) and Perinthalmanna (Kerala) were collected from a depth of 0-20 cm. These were then processed as usual and analysed⁵ for certain of their physico-chemical properties reported in the paper.

Before taking the infra-red curves, these soils were separated from visible organic matters, pulverised in an agate-mortar and then passed through 100-mesh (British Standard) sieve. The soils were then subjected to different infrared treatments. The IR-curves were obtained by KBr-mull technique and the apparatus used was Perkin-Elmer Infrared Spectrophotometer 137. The KBr-mull technique for obtaining the I.R.-curves the soil samples was used due to the fact that KBr does not absorb the

infrared light in the region between 2.5 μ to 15 μ (our range of study) and therefore a complete spectrum of the particular soil sample is obtained.

The infrared curves of each soil sample have been studied in the wavelength 2.5 μ to 15 μ to which particular regions for Si-OH (bonded and unbonded or structural water-peak); Si-OH (absorbed water-peak); Si-O (silica-peak); Al-O (Alumina-peak); Si-H (pH-peak) and Si-C (carbon complex-peak). The infrared absorption peaks have been allocated³ for each of these functional groups mentioned have been given in Table 1.

The depths of IR-peaks (I/I_0) were calculated by 'base line technique'⁶ and reported in Table 1.

The regression (or straight line) equations between the depth of IR-peaks and different soil properties were also reported here. However, in Table 3, only those straight line equations have been given and discussed in the text which were found to be significant at 5% level of significance.

Results and Discussion

The distribution of different characteristic I.R. absorption peaks referred in the infrared region of the functional groups (i.e., Si-OH, Si-O, Al-O, Si-H and Si-C) for all the fifteen acidic soils of India (Figs. 1-4) has been given in Table 1. The depth of IR-peaks (I/I_0) and transmittance percentage (denoted here by the symbol S, M and W) of each infrared absorption peaks have also been given in the same table. It may be observed that the characteristics of IR-curves of each soil sample vary according to the nature of the soil.

The total number of peaks in the respective IR-curves of acidic soils are found mostly 10 although a few soils (viz., Koraput, Darjeeling, Nilgiris and Ratnagiri soils) have been found to record the total number of peaks equal to 11. The total number of

TABLE 1—INFRARED ABSORPTION PEAKS OF DIFFERENT ACIDIC SOILS

Soil	WAVE LENGTH (μ)						Fig. No.	Total number of peaks
	Si-OH (Bonded & un- bonded water peaks)	Si-OH (Absorbed water peaks)	Si-O (Silica- peak)	Al-O (Alumina- peak)	Si-H (pH-peak)	Si-C (Carbon-peak)		
	2.70-3.50	4.20-8.00	8.50-9.50	9.50-10.30	10.95-11.30	12.0-15.0		
1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Almorah	2.75, 2.95 (M) (M) 1.60, 1.50	4.30, 6.15 (M) (M) 1.20, 1.16	9.10 (S) 7.0	9.75 (S) 11.36	11.00 (M) 1.77	12.50, 13.55, 14.45 (M) (M) (M) 1.06 1.30, 1.11	1	10
Mirzapur	2.95, 3.0 (M) (M) 1.60, 1.54	4.30, 6.15 (M) (M) 1.10, 1.28	9.10 (M) 2.37	9.75 (S) 7.0	10.95 (M) 1.85	12.50, 12.85, 14.45 (M) (M) (M) 1.33, 1.36, 1.82	2	10
Ranchi	2.95, 3.50 (M) (M) 1.50, 1.50	4.30, 6.15, 8.0 (M) (M) (M) 1.15, 1.25, 1.55	9.10 (S) 3.60	9.75 (S) 7.80	11.0 (M) 1.93	12.50, 14.45 (M) (M) 1.37, 1.18	3	10
Dhanbad	2.95, 3.10 (M) (M) 1.43, 1.26	4.30, 6.15 (M) (M) 1.36, 1.41	9.10 (M) 2.80	9.75 (S) 5.36	10.95 (M) 1.76	12.50, 13.20, 14.45 (M) (M) (M) 1.25, 1.13, 1.16	4	10
Lakhimpur	2.95 (M) 1.37	4.30, 5.25, 6.15 (W) (W) (M) 1.17, 1.04, 1.24	9.10 (S) 4.20	9.75 (S) 6.91	11.0 (M) 6.90	12.50, 13.10, 14.45 (M) (M) (M) 1.47, 1.27, 1.10	5	10
Koraput	2.80, 2.95, 3.50 (M) (M) (M) 1.36, 1.36, 1.21	6.15, 4.30, 6.80 (M) (M) (M) 1.32, 1.24, 1.20	9.10 (M) 2.50	9.75 (S) 6.15	10.95 (M) 1.71	12.50, 14.45 (M) (M) 1.30, 1.14	6	11
Burdwan	2.80, 2.95 (M) (M) 1.46, 1.20	4.30, 6.15 (W) (W) 1.12, 1.22	9.10 (M) 3.46	9.75 (S) 6.86	10.95 (M) 1.27	12.50, 12.80, 14.45 (M) (M) (M) 1.34, 1.35, 1.17	7	10
Darjeeling	2.80, 2.95 (M) (M) 1.78, 1.68	4.30, 6.15 (M) (M) 1.16, 1.05	9.10 (M) 3.60	9.75, 10.00 (S) (S) 11.66, 7.44	10.95 (M) 2.26	12.50, 13.35, 14.45 (M) (M) (M) 1.74, 1.15, 1.22	8	11
Godavari	2.80, 2.95 (M) (M) 1.53, 1.21	4.30, 6.15 (M) (M) 1.36, 1.12	9.10 (S) 3.70	9.75 (S) 5.70	10.95 (M) 1.57	12.50, 12.85, 14.45 (M) (M) (M) 1.46, 1.33, 1.23	9	10
Bangalore	2.80, 2.95 (M) (M) 1.42, 1.36	4.30, 6.15 (M) (M) 1.36, 1.46	9.10 (M) 2.30	9.75, 10.00 (S) (S) 4.72, 3.40	10.95 (M) 1.65	12.50, 14.45 (M) (M) 1.07, 1.12	10	10
Mandeya	2.80, 2.95 (M) (M) 1.57, 1.60	4.30, 6.15, 6.80 (M) (M) (M) 1.11, 1.26, 1.09	9.10 (M) 2.31	9.75 (S) 4.93	10.95 (M) 1.65	12.50, 14.45 (M) (M) 1.08, 1.12	11	10
Nilgiris	2.80, 2.95 (M) (M) 1.37, 1.35	4.30, 6.15 (M) (M) 1.17, 1.74	9.10 (S) 3.20	9.75, 10.00 (S) (S) 3.45, 5.40	11.0 (M) 1.06	12.50, 13.35, 14.45 (M) (M) (M) 1.06, 1.06, 1.06	12	11
Poona	2.80, 2.95 (M) (M) 1.46, 1.08	4.30, 6.15 (M) (M) 1.13, 1.18	9.10 (M) 2.75	9.75 (S) 5.46	10.95 (M) 1.68	12.50, 13.50, 14.45 (M) (M) (M) 1.22, 1.20, 1.16	13	10
Ratnagiri	2.75, 2.95 (M) (M) 1.50, 1.44	4.30, 6.15 (W) (W) 1.13, 1.17	9.10 (S) 3.30	9.75, 9.95 (S) (S) 9.44, 6.45	11.00 (M) 1.82	12.50, 13.35, 14.45 (M) (M) (M) 1.02, 1.08, 1.19	14	11
Perinthal manna	2.75, 2.95 (M) (M) 1.46, 1.45	4.30, 6.15 (W) (M) 1.13, 1.43	9.10 (M) 2.50	9.70 (S) 6.07	10.95 (M) 1.66	12.50, 13.10, 14.45 (M) (M) (M) 1.08, 1.04, 1.13	15	10

Note : 1. S—Strong (Transmittance below 25%) ; M=Medium (T between 25 to 75%) ; W = Weak (T above 75%).
2. The second figures indicate the depth of IR-peaks (I/I₀).

Fig 1
I.R. Curve of of Poona Soil (13)
" " Mirzapur Soil (2)
" " Almorah Soil (1)
" " Darjeeling Soil (8)

Fig 2
I.R. Curve of Bangalore Soil (10)
" " Godavari Soil (9)
" " Dhanbad Soil (4)
" " Mandeya Soil (11)

TABLE 2—SOME PHYSICO-CHEMICAL PROPERTIES OF ACIDIC SOILS

Soil	PROPERTIES								Texture
	SiO ₂ %	R ₂ O ₃ %	Al ₂ O ₃ %	CaO + MgO %	N %	C %	b.e.c, meq/100g.	pH	
Almorah	88.00	9.70	7.00	1.20	0.08	0.89	15.60	6.20	Sandy Loam
Mirzapur	82.60	12.20	9.20	1.30	0.06	0.41	10.50	6.30	-do-
Ranchi	85.60	12.00	9.30	0.94	0.07	0.65	8.20	6.40	-do-
Dhanbad	95.40	4.36	3.06	0.72	0.09	0.34	23.47	6.80	Loamy Sand
Lakhimpur	89.68	13.36	10.52	1.18	0.10	0.63	12.50	6.60	Sandy Clay Loam
Koraput	70.22	7.62	5.07	0.39	0.05	0.40	17.76	6.30	-do-
Burdwan	85.62	13.86	12.06	0.76	0.17	0.72	24.56	6.80	Loam
Darjeeling	82.85	16.72	13.92	0.60	0.06	0.44	18.80	5.20	Sandy Clay Loam
Godavari	95.41	4.15	2.35	2.70	0.03	0.19	20.17	6.20	Sandy loam
Bangalore	86.14	12.81	9.57	1.35	0.12	1.59	20.80	6.30	Sandy clay Loam
Mandeya	83.85	11.96	10.79	1.12	0.05	0.47	18.20	6.80	-do-
Nilgiris	77.28	15.02	11.11	2.96	0.07	0.60	20.20	5.50	-do-
Poona	60.28	34.71	29.51	1.40	0.08	0.83	22.50	6.40	Loam
Ratnagiri	65.10	42.00	39.84	1.24	0.17	0.86	23.00	5.70	Sandy Clay Loam
Perinthalmanna	78.02	18.00	12.32	0.76	0.06	0.48	19.56	6.70	-do-

Fig. 3
I.R. Curve of Lakhimpur Soil (5)
" " Kerala Soil (15)
" " Ratnagiri Soil (14)
" " Nilgiri Soil (12)

Fig. 4
I.R. Curve of Burdwan Soil (7)
" " Koraput Soil (6)
" " Ranchi Soil (3)

TABLE 3—STRAIGHT LINE EQUATIONS OBTAINED BETWEEN THE DEPTH OF IR-PEAKS (x) AND SOIL PROPERTIES (y)

Soil properties	FUNCTIONAL GROUPS					
	Si-OH (Structural water-peak) y =	Si-OH (Absorbed water-peak) y =	Si-O (Silica-peak) y =	Al-O (Alumina-peak) y =	Si-H (pH-peak) y =	Si-C (Carbon peak) y =
SiO ₂ %	-5.63 × +90.92	7.38 × +77.70	1.80 × +77.70	-0.54 × +93.13	-7.47 × +25.87	6.72 × +74.96
R ₂ O ₃ %	10.28 × -4.42	-13.97 × +29.80	1.36 × +10.38	—	—	-21.33 × +38.82
Al ₂ O ₃ %	45.60 × -55.84	—	—	—	—	—
CaO+MgO%	2.75 × -1.78	0.70 × +1.60	—	—	0.03 × +0.02	-0.15 × + 0.25
N%	-0.60 × -0.94	-0.08 × +0.17	—	—	-0.23 × +0.97	—
C%	0.76 × -0.50	—	0.19 × +0.14	—	-3.77 × +19.48	-16.38 × +37.93
b.e.c.	×	—	2.16 × +13.16	—	—	—
Meq%	—	—	—	—	—	—
pH	-0.25 × +11.60	1.75 × +5.25	0.81 × +5.48	—	0.02 × +7.30	—

peaks of different acidic soils indicate clearly that these are useful for agricultural crop production. De³ pointed out that 'any arable soil having more than 6 total number of peaks in its IR-curve may be termed fertile'.

The characteristic IR-absorption peaks of all the fifteen acidic soils of India indicate that there are some common IR-peak values (Table 1) for all the soils which may well be said to be the peak values which can be utilized for their identification. These common peak values are 2.95 for Si-OH (structural water-peak), 4.30 μ , 6.15 μ for Si-OH (absorbed water-peak); 9.10 μ for Si-O (silica-peak); 9.75 μ for Al-O (alumina-peak); 10.95 μ or 11.0 μ for Si-H (*pH*-peak) and 12.50 μ , 14.45 μ for Si-C (carbon-peak infrared region). These common peak values may also be utilized for knowing the nature of the constituting atoms and their bonds forming the particular functional group (di-atomic polyatomic molecule) for which these peak values stand for.

The number of smaller IR-absorption peaks in the wave-length region between 4.50 μ to 7.50 μ of each IR-curves are generally found to tally well with the b.e.c. of the corresponding soil samples (cf. Figs. 1 to 4 and Table 2). De⁴ also pointed out that the total number of smaller IR-peaks in the wavelength region 4.50 μ to 7.50 μ are approx. equal to the b.e.c. of the respective soils.

De³ pointed out that the Si-H (*pH*-peak) functional group in the wavelength region between 11.00 μ to 11.20 μ may be considered for the prediction of soil *pH*. The infrared absorption peak for this functional group in our case, have been found to occur mostly at 10.95 μ . Five soils (viz., Almorah, Ranchi, Lakhimpur, Nilgiris and Ratnagiri soils) however, recorded this IR-absorption peak value at 11.0 μ . Distinct presence of this peak (Figs. 1-4) in the IR-curves of soils clearly indicates that the soils (taken in our experiment also) are acidic in nature. Since H of Si-H functional group known is to be loosely bound and is in the exchangeable form at the exchange complex and this perhaps can be used for the prediction of soil *pH*. In alkali soils this infrared absorption peak at the mentioned region is always found to be very weak, less prominent and sometimes even absent. The total number of IR-absorption peaks in the wavelength region allotted to

Si-C (carbon peak) group is generally found to be three and commonly occurred at the wavelength values 12.50 μ and 14.45 μ (Table 1).

Some of the physico-chemical properties of the soils in relation to the depths of IR-peaks reported in the paper have generally been found to be significant at 5% level of significance (Table 3). The properties are SiO₂ (negative), R₂O₃, Al₂O₃, CaO+MgO, N (negative), C (all in percent), *pH* with Si-OH (bonded and unbonded water-peak); SiO₂%, R₂O₃% (negative), CaO+MgO%, N% (negative), *pH* with Si-OH (Absorbed water-peak); SiO₂, R₂O₃, C(all in percent), b.e.c. meq.% with Si-O (Silica-peak), SiO₂% (negative) with Al-O (Alumina-peak); R₂O₃ (negative), C (negative), N (all the percent), *pH*, b.e.c. meq % with Si-H (*pH*-peak) and R₂O₃ (negative), C (negative), N (all in percent), *pH*, b.e.c. meq. % (negative) with Si-C (carbon-peak) functional groups.

The regression equations obtained between the depth of IR-peaks and different soil properties (which are found) to be significant at 5% level of significance have been given in Table 3. These equations may well be used for the quantitative determination of different soil analysates (soil properties here) if the IR-curves of the unknown soil samples and depth of IR-absorptions peaks in such IR-curves of soils are available. These equations can prove useful for routine analysis of soils by infrared spectrophotometry.

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